

Actual vs Predicted (AverageTemp)

Standardized Residuals (AverageTemp)

Partial Regression Plot (AverageTemp)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.4212$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 0.9970

p-value: 0.3180

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

White Test

White Statistic: 0.9983

df: 2

p-value: 0.6070

Conclusion: No Heteroskedasticity

Histogram of Residuals (AverageTemp)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – AverageTemp

